

Analytical method development and validation for the determination of triazole antifungals in biological matrices

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Abstract

The World Health Organization released the fungal priority pathogen list (FPPL) in late 2022, identifying fungal pathogens in urgent need of research and intervention. Triazole antifungals, as first-line therapy, require therapeutic drug monitoring to optimize outcomes because of their narrow therapeutic range and interindividual pharmacokinetic variability. The bioanalysis process is challenging due to complex matrices. This study aimed to develop and validate an analytical method for quantifying voriconazole, itraconazole, and fluconazole in human plasma using high-performance liquid chromatography with an imprinted polymer sorbent. Optimization employed a C₁₈ column with isocratic elution (acetonitrile:water 70:30, v/v) at a flow rate of 1 mL/min and detection at 260 nm. Retention times were 2.467, 3.487, and 9.006 minutes for fluconazole, voriconazole, and itraconazole, respectively. System suitability testing met chromatographic requirements. The validated bioanalytical method complies with U.S. FDA guidelines, demonstrating linearity over the 0.5–5 mg/L range. Maximum percent bias was 13.4% for the calibration curve, 15.6% at the LLOQ, and 12.9% above the LLOQ. Precision showed a maximum coefficient of variation of 12.9%, confirming the method's accuracy and reproducibility. The molecularly imprinted solid-phase extraction (MISPE) method showed superior selectivity and recovery compared with commercial C₁₈ SPE cartridges. This study establishes a reliable method for future clinical sample applications.

Keywords

bioanalysis, method validation, MISPE, sample preparation, triazole antifungals

Introduction

The World Health Organization released the fungal priority pathogen list (FPPL) in late 2022 to encourage global research into fungal diseases and antifungal resistance. There are three priority classifications for the 19 species

that cause invasive fungal diseases: critical, high, and medium. *Candida auris*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, and *Candida albicans* are four fungi categorized as critical groups (Fisher and Denning 2023). The epidemiology of invasive fungal infections warrants attention due to their high mortality rates—around 30–70%

in invasive aspergillosis and 40% in invasive candidiasis (Firacative 2020). Furthermore, *Aspergillus* spp. and *Candida* spp. have been identified as the predominant fungal pathogens responsible for complications in patients with COVID-19, leading to fungal coinfection (Song et al. 2020; Talento and Hoenigl 2020). The guidelines provided by the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) recommend triazole-class antifungal agents as a primary treatment option for the prevention and management of invasive aspergillosis and candidiasis (Patterson et al. 2016). Among the various systemic antifungal compounds used in managing invasive fungal infections—such as polyenes (e.g., amphotericin B), triazoles (e.g., fluconazole, itraconazole, voriconazole, posaconazole, and isavuconazole), echinocandins (e.g., caspofungin, micafungin, and anidulafungin), and flucytosine—those most strongly recommended for therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) include voriconazole, itraconazole, posaconazole, and 5-flucytosine. In contrast, amphotericin B, echinocandins, fluconazole, and isavuconazole are not routinely indicated for TDM (Gómez-López 2020).

Guidelines from well-established organizations such as the IDSA and the British Society for Medical Mycology advocate systematic TDM in patients receiving triazole antifungals, primarily due to their variable pharmacokinetics and the potential correlation between serum drug concentrations, therapeutic efficacy, and toxicity (Ashbee et al. 2014; Pappas et al. 2016; Patterson et al. 2016). Routine TDM is particularly warranted for voriconazole owing to its pronounced interindividual pharmacokinetic variability. Moreover, its therapeutic use necessitates caution due to the risk of neurotoxicity and hepatotoxicity, with an optimal plasma concentration range generally considered to be between 1 and 5 mg/L (Luong et al. 2016). For itraconazole, the primary rationale for TDM is its unpredictable oral bioavailability and the potential for drug-drug interactions, complicating the establishment of an optimal dosing regimen. The suggested therapeutic concentration range for itraconazole is approximately 0.5–1 mg/L (Glasmacher et al. 1999). Although fluconazole is generally characterized by predictable pharmacokinetic properties and therefore not routinely subjected to TDM, dose adjustment may be required in certain clinical scenarios—particularly in patients with complex pathophysiological conditions such as renal impairment, where altered drug clearance may affect therapeutic outcomes (Sinnollareddy et al. 2015).

Triazole antifungal agents can be quantified through various analytical techniques, including titrimetric methods and instrumental approaches such as spectrophotometry, electrochemical analysis, and chromatography. However, titrimetric and spectrophotometric methods are generally unsuitable for the analysis of triazole antifungals in complex matrices, such as biological samples, due to their limited selectivity and sensitivity (Ekiert et al. 2010). Chromatographic methods—particularly high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UPLC)—are the most

widely used and thoroughly developed techniques for determining triazole antifungal concentrations in biological matrices. Several HPLC-based protocols have been established, utilizing various sample preparation techniques in combination with different detection systems, including ultraviolet (UV) detectors (Mei et al. 2013; Campestre et al. 2017), mass spectrometry (MS) (Baietto et al. 2010; Fatiguso et al. 2017), and tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) (Beste et al. 2012; Xiao et al. 2017; Jenkins et al. 2018). Although fluconazole, voriconazole, and itraconazole are rarely prescribed together in clinical settings, a simultaneous analytical method for these compounds offers practical advantages for laboratory workflows. Having a single method capable of analyzing all three drugs efficiently allows laboratories to streamline their processes, saving time, reducing costs, and minimizing solvent use during routine quality control and therapeutic drug monitoring.

Biological matrices—including serum, plasma, and tissue samples—are composed of a range of endogenous constituents, such as proteins, lipids, salts, and metabolites. These components contribute to matrix complexity, posing challenges for analytical processes aimed at isolating and quantifying target analytes, which may share similar physicochemical properties with the analyte of interest. The selection of an appropriate sample preparation technique is influenced by the physicochemical characteristics of the analyte and its metabolites (Acquavia et al. 2021). Commonly applied techniques in the preparation of triazole antifungals in biological matrices include protein precipitation (Imoto et al. 2020; Lu et al. 2022), liquid-liquid extraction (Al-Ghobashy et al. 2018; Moreira et al. 2020), solid-phase extraction (Bashir et al. 2020; Zarad et al. 2021), or a combination thereof. These methods serve to extract the analyte, eliminate interfering substances, and concentrate the target compound before chromatographic separation (Zheng and Wang 2019). Bioanalytical method validation must be performed to ensure the robustness and reliability of a procedure intended for quantifying analytes in biological matrices (FDA 2018). Simultaneous analysis of triazole antifungal agents in biological matrices requires highly selective separation techniques. Therefore, the development of optimized sample preparation procedures and analytical methods is essential for accurate and reliable quantification.

Previous studies have successfully synthesized molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) as sorbents for solid-phase extraction (Gunawan et al. 2024). However, comprehensive development and validation of analytical and bioanalytical methods for detecting triazole antifungals extracted using MIPs have not yet been conducted. This molecular imprinting process entails the polymerization of functional monomers and cross-linking agents in the presence of the target analytes, resulting in a cross-linked polymer matrix containing recognition sites with high specificity (He et al. 2021). The high specificity of MIPs arises from the incorporation of a template molecule—typically the target analyte—during the polymerization process, which serves as a structural mold for the

formation of selective recognition sites within the polymer matrix. The target molecule exhibits structural and functional complementarity to these recognition sites, enabling MIPs to function as synthetic receptors, as illustrated in Fig. 1. In contrast to the widespread use of conventional C_{18} sorbents in the bioanalysis of triazole-class antifungal agents, the present study employed an MIP sorbent for the selective extraction of triazole compounds. The imprinted cavities within the polymer can selectively bind the target analyte with defined affinity and spatial orientation, thereby enhancing analytical specificity. Due to these properties, MIPs facilitate highly selective detection and quantification of target compounds (Sajini and Mathew 2021). This approach offers superior selectivity and extraction efficiency compared with conventional solid-phase extraction methods, making it particularly advantageous for complex sample matrices and trace-level analyte detection, such as in bioanalytical applications (Suzaei et al. 2022). With the selectivity of MIP, this study aims to develop and validate an analytical method for the simultaneous determination of selected triazole antifungal agents—voriconazole, itraconazole, and fluconazole—in human plasma using high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with UV detection.

Materials and methods

Materials

Instruments

Instruments used in this study included a Beckman Coulter DU720 UV/Vis spectrophotometer, a Waters e2695 HPLC system with UV detector and Zorbax Eclipse Plus C_{18} column, a JASCO 4200 FTIR spectrometer, a Wiseclean WUC-D06H ultrasonic cleaner, a Binder ED 056 oven, a DLAB MS-H280-Pro magnetic stirrer with heater, a Biosan PSU-20i orbital shaker, a Waters SPE vacuum manifold, and standard laboratory glassware.

Chemicals

All reagents and chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade unless otherwise specified. The triazole antifungal agents—voriconazole (VOR), itraconazole (ITR), and fluconazole (FLU)—were obtained from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI). For HPLC analysis, solvents including acetonitrile (ACN) and methanol (MET), along with acetone (ACE), chloroform (CHL), dichloromethane (DCM), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and glacial acetic acid, all of analytical grade, were sourced from Merck. Human plasma samples were provided by Palang Merah Indonesia (PMI).

HPLC system optimization

The development of a concurrent analytical method for triazole antifungal agents via HPLC commenced with the optimization of raw materials, with particular emphasis on

variables affecting chromatographic separation. The optimization process was conducted using a one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) approach. Parameters optimized included column type, elution mode, mobile-phase composition, flow rate, detection wavelength, and injection volume. Each parameter was optimized individually to identify the most favorable conditions for achieving optimal chromatographic separation and accurate quantification of the triazole antifungal agents. The goal was to establish an optimal system suitable for reliable quantification. After determining the optimal settings using OFAT, the performance of the selected conditions was verified through a system suitability test to ensure compliance with established criteria for repeatability, tailing factor, capacity factor, number of theoretical plates, and resolution.

Analytical method validation

The optimized HPLC system was subjected to method validation to ensure its reliability and suitability for the simultaneous analysis of triazole antifungal agents as guidance for subsequent bioanalytical method development and molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) adsorption study. The validation parameters included specificity, linearity, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), accuracy, and precision, as outlined in established analytical guidelines (European Medicines Agency ICH 2005; Sahu et al. 2018). Specificity was assessed by injecting both the triazole standard solution and the diluent into the chromatographic system. The method was deemed specific if no interfering peaks appeared at the retention times corresponding to the target analytes. Linearity was evaluated by preparing standard solutions of the triazole compounds at concentrations of 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, and 5.0 mg/L. Each solution was analyzed by HPLC, and the corresponding chromatographic peak areas were recorded. The method satisfied the linearity requirement if the correlation coefficient (r) approached 1.000. The LOD and LOQ were determined using the standard deviation of the residuals (S_y/x) obtained from the linearity data. Accuracy and intraday precision were evaluated by preparing standard solutions of the triazoles at concentrations of 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 mg/L, which represent 80%, 100%, and 120% of the target concentration of the dissolved and diluted raw materials. Each concentration level was analyzed in triplicate. The peak areas were recorded, and the percentage recovery and relative standard deviation (RSD) were determined. The method was considered accurate if the recovery values were within 98.0–102.0% and precise if the RSD values did not exceed 2.0%. Inter-day precision was assessed by preparing six replicates of a 2.5 mg/L standard solution, analyzed on two different days. In the intermediate precision study, a one-sided chi-square test was used to verify that the RSD between two different days did not exceed 2%. Additionally, a paired t-test was conducted to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference in mean recovery between the two days.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of MIP formation (Saylan et al. 2019).

Optimization of solid-phase extraction system

The solid-phase extraction (SPE) procedure was optimized to enhance the selective retention and recovery of triazole antifungal compounds. The optimal MIP from a previous study was packed into 200 mg empty SPE cartridges to form the MIP sorbent-based SPE (MISPE). Key parameters investigated included the choice of conditioning, sample loading, washing, and elution solvents. A standard solution containing 2.5 mg/L FLU, VOR, and ITR was used as the reference. The solvent type in each step was systematically optimized to ensure effective interaction between the analytes and the MISPE while minimizing nonspecific binding and matrix interference. The optimization process aimed to maximize analyte recovery and improve the overall efficiency and reproducibility of the MISPE process before HPLC analysis. Extraction efficiency of the MISPE system was assessed by comparing the chromatographic response of a 2.5 mg/L triazole standard solution processed through the MISPE system with that of a standard solution directly injected into the HPLC system.

Plasma sample preparation

A volume of 0.2 mL of blood plasma was spiked with a 2.5 mg/L triazole standard solution prepared in a 1:1 (v/v) mixture of ACN and water. The volume ratio between plasma and standard solution was optimized to evaluate potential matrix effects. The ACN-water mixture was selected because it precipitates approximately 99.9% of plasma proteins and is compatible with the HPLC system (Pedersen-Bjergaard et al. 2015). Protein precipitation of blood plasma was carried out by vortex mixing the sample at 3000 rpm for 2 minutes, followed by centrifugation at 13,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant was filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter and subsequently

passed through a preconditioned MISPE cartridge. The column was washed with 2×1 mL of water, and the analyte was eluted using 2×1 mL of MET. The eluate was evaporated to dryness, reconstituted with 1 mL of the mobile phase, and injected into the HPLC system.

Bioanalytical method validation

Bioanalytical method validation was conducted by evaluating key parameters, including linearity, accuracy, and precision (FDA 2018). This study was performed to ensure the reliability of the method in clinical applications. Calibration standards were prepared by spiking plasma samples with triazoles at seven concentration levels (0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, and 5.0 mg/L), each in five replicates. Linearity was assessed based on the deviation from the nominal concentration, with acceptable bias set within $\pm 15\%$, except for the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ), which was allowed a deviation of $\pm 20\%$. Accuracy and precision were evaluated using quality control (QC) samples at four concentration levels: LLOQ (0.5 mg/L), low (QCL, 1.0 mg/L), medium (QCM, 2.5 mg/L), and high (QCH, 5.0 mg/L), each prepared in quintuplicate. Analyses were conducted both within a single run and across three separate days to evaluate intra- and inter-day variability. The acceptance criteria for accuracy and precision required that the bias and coefficient of variation (RSD) remain within $\pm 15\%$ for all QC levels, except for the LLOQ, where a tolerance of $\pm 20\%$ was permitted.

Comparison with the established method

The performance of the MISPE sorbent was systematically evaluated and compared with that of commercially available C_{18} SPE cartridges, which are the most commonly used sorbents in triazole antifungal bioanalysis. This assessment focused on the sorbents' ability to simultaneously separate

triazole antifungal agents from blood plasma. Additionally, the comparison with C_{18} SPE cartridges, widely used in analytical chemistry for similar applications, provided a benchmark to assess the relative advantages of MISPE in terms of sensitivity, specificity, and overall performance in complex biological samples such as blood plasma.

Results and discussion

HPLC system optimization

This study specifically focused on the triazole antifungal agents VOR, ITR, and FLU, as these are the only representatives of their class currently available in formulated pharmaceutical preparations within the Indonesian market, as illustrated in Fig. 2. This targeted approach ensures that the method can be effectively implemented in hospital laboratories or other clinical environments for purposes such as TDM, assessment of patient compliance, dose adjustment, and pharmacokinetic profiling (Voulgaridou et al. 2023). Furthermore, focusing on the antifungal agents currently accessible to practitioners and patients strengthens the method's applicability and immediate utility, bridging the gap between research outcomes and clinical practice.

Figure 2. Chemical structures of voriconazole (a), fluconazole (b), and itraconazole (c).

OFAT optimization

The development and validation of a simultaneous analytical method for VOR, ITR, and FLU using HPLC began with a systematic optimization process. The initial method for HPLC system development was adapted and modified from an existing method (Choudhary et al. 2021), with adjustments made to key chromatographic parameters affecting separation efficiency. The optimization was performed using the OFAT approach,

with evaluation metrics such as capacity factor, injection repeatability, resolution, selectivity, tailing factor, and theoretical plate count. This method involves adjusting one variable at a time while keeping all other factors constant, allowing the researchers to isolate the effect of each parameter on chromatographic performance. By systematically changing one factor—such as column type, flow rate, mobile-phase type, mobile-phase composition, injection volume, and detection wavelength—the optimal values for each parameter were determined. The objective was to establish a robust and reliable method suitable for both qualitative and quantitative analyses. The optimal chromatographic separation of FLU, VOR, and ITR was successfully achieved using a reversed-phase HPLC system, with elution occurring sequentially at approximately 2.467 minutes for fluconazole, 3.487 minutes for voriconazole, and 9.006 minutes for itraconazole. This elution order corresponds to differences in the physicochemical properties and structural features of the analytes. In reversed-phase chromatography, analyte retention is predominantly governed by hydrophobic interactions with the nonpolar stationary phase, where compounds with greater lipophilicity exhibit longer retention times (Gilroy et al. 2003; Ganesh et al. 2023). Fluconazole, which eluted first, is a relatively small and polar compound characterized by two triazole rings, a difluorophenyl moiety, and a hydroxyl group. These functional groups contribute to its hydrophilic nature and result in limited interaction with the hydrophobic stationary phase. Voriconazole, which shares structural similarities with fluconazole, contains additional aromatic and halogenated substituents, conferring increased molecular weight and moderate lipophilicity, thus leading to slightly longer retention. Itraconazole, in contrast, is a substantially larger molecule with multiple aromatic rings and ether linkages and exhibits high lipophilicity. These structural attributes enhance its affinity for the stationary phase, resulting in the longest retention time. The observed retention trend (FLU < VOR < ITR) is therefore consistent with increasing molecular size and hydrophobic character, confirming the effectiveness of the developed method in resolving triazole antifungals based on their structural and physicochemical differences (Peyton et al. 2015; Guan et al. 2024). The most optimal HPLC conditions and chromatographic results for the simultaneous analysis of triazole antifungals are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 3.

Table 1. Optimized HPLC conditions.

Parameter	Specification
HPLC system	HPLC with UV detector
Column	C_{18} (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile phase	Water:acetonitrile (30:70, v/v), isocratic
Flow rate	1.0 mL/min
Injection volume	50 μL
Detection wavelength	260 nm
Retention time	10 minutes
Diluent	Acetonitrile

Figure 3. Chromatogram of the optimized HPLC method.

System suitability test

Following the optimization of chromatographic conditions, a system suitability test (SST) was conducted to assess the performance and reliability of the analytical system. As a critical component of method verification, the SST ensures that the system operates within predefined parameters to deliver consistent and accurate results. Key performance criteria—including retention time stability, column efficiency (theoretical plates), peak symmetry (tailing factor), resolution, and capacity factor—were evaluated to determine system adequacy. All measured parameters met the established acceptance criteria, indicating that the system functioned with the required precision, selectivity, and reproducibility, as shown in Table 2. The consistency of these metrics across replicate injections confirms the robustness of the method, supporting its suitability for routine quantitative analysis in an analytical context.

Analytical method validation

The fully optimized HPLC method was rigorously validated to ensure its analytical robustness and applicability for the simultaneous quantification of VOR, ITR, and FLU in plasma matrices. This validation, conducted in accordance with established regulatory standards, encompassed evaluations of specificity, linearity, sensitivity (LOD and LOQ), accuracy, precision, and intermediate precision (Ermer 2025). Specificity assessment confirmed the method's selectivity, as no interfering peaks were observed in chromatograms of matrices, thereby verifying the distinct resolution of each target analyte from other components (Fig. 4). Linearity was demonstrated across the calibration range for each compound, with correlation coefficients of 0.999 for FLU and 1.000 for both VOR and ITR, indicating a strong linear relationship between analyte concentration and detector response, reflecting consistent calibration performance.

Table 2. HPLC system suitability test.

Fluconazole						
Injection	RT	AUC	T	k	N	Rs
1	2.460	186,390	1.083	0.402	4,544	NA
2	2.449	185,681	1.084	0.395	4,714	
3	2.446	188,426	1.078	0.394	4,537	
4	2.450	184,252	1.091	0.396	4,742	
5	2.447	188,882	1.074	0.394	4,634	
6	2.455	183,974	1.076	0.400	4,669	
Average	2.451	186,267.5	1.081	0.397	4,640.049	
Stdev	0.005	2,057.965	0.006	0.003	85.591	
RSD	0.218	1.105	0.596	0.827	1.845	
Voriconazole						
Injection	RT	AUC	T	k	N	Rs
1	3.480	122,296	1.062	0.977	6,767	6.546
2	3.471	122,351	1.062	0.972	6,771	6.599
3	3.466	122,011	1.070	0.969	6,780	6.594
4	3.470	122,326	1.066	0.971	6,802	6.595
5	3.463	122,126	1.063	0.967	6,789	6.590
6	3.470	121,880	1.063	0.971	6,916	6.604
Average	3.470	122,165.000	1.064	0.971	6,804.182	6.588
Stdev	0.006	191.906	0.003	0.003	56.248	0.021
RSD	0.166	0.157	0.284	0.335	0.827	0.321
Itraconazole						
Injection	RT	AUC	T	k	N	Rs
1	8.998	290,429	1.001	4.112	9,114	20.367
2	9.004	291,048	0.997	4.116	9,095	20.386
3	8.980	291,375	0.999	4.103	9,117	20.435
4	8.977	292,248	1.000	4.101	9,228	20.483
5	8.953	291,489	1.000	4.087	9,336	20.522
6	8.955	290,640	1.000	4.088	9,482	20.664
Average	8.978	291,204.833	1.000	4.101	9,228.604	20.476
Stdev	0.021	654.745	0.002	0.012	154.316	0.109
RSD	0.235	0.225	0.155	0.291	1.672	0.531

RT: retention time; T: tailing factor; k: capacity factor; N: theoretical plate numbers; Rs: resolution.

Sensitivity was determined using the signal-to-noise method, yielding LOD values of 0.60 mg/L for FLU, 0.18 mg/L for VOR, and 0.45 mg/L for ITR. Corresponding LOQ values

Figure 4. Specificity test results (green: triazole standard; red: diluent).

were 1.82 mg/L, 0.55 mg/L, and 1.37 mg/L, demonstrating the method's capability to detect and quantify low concentrations of each analyte with sufficient sensitivity for subsequent bioanalytical applications. Accuracy and precision were evaluated at three QC levels (80%, 100%, and 120% of nominal concentrations). All values met the predefined acceptance limits. At 80%, mean recoveries were 99.9% (FLU), 100.4% (VOR), and 98.4% (ITR), with RSDs of 0.8%, 0.1%, and 0.1%, respectively. At 100%, recoveries were 99.5%, 99.6%, and 100.5%, with RSDs of 0.4%, 0.3%, and 0.3%. At 120%, recoveries were 98.4%, 97.3%, and 100.3%, with RSDs of 0.7%, 0.1%, and 0.2%, respectively. Intermediate precision was evaluated statistically using a one-sided chi-square test and a paired t-test. The chi-square test confirmed that the RSDs between the two testing days did not exceed 2%, as indicated by a non-significant result [$P(\text{RSD} \leq 2\%) > 0.05$]. Furthermore, the paired t-test showed no statistically significant difference in mean recovery between the two days [$P(|t| \geq 2.57) > 0.05$], suggesting that the average recovery remained consistent. These findings support the conclusion that the method demonstrates acceptable reproducibility across the two testing periods. In summary, the validated method fulfilled all performance criteria, as shown in Table 3, demonstrating its reliability for the simultaneous quantification of triazole antifungal agents in plasma and confirming its suitability for analytical applications.

Optimization of solid-phase extraction system

An evaluation was conducted to assess the performance of cartridges containing MIP particles as sorbents in SPE (MISPE). The optimization consisted of four steps. The first step was sorbent conditioning, which served to activate or wet the sorbent and remove potential contaminants present on the sorbent material. This step ensured that the sorbent was in an optimal state for analyte retention. The second stage involved sample loading, where the sample was introduced into the SPE column containing the conditioned sorbent. In this phase, the sorbent interacted with the analytes of interest and retained them through specific physicochemical interactions. The third stage was the washing step, which aimed to eliminate matrix components and other unwanted substances that could interfere with subsequent analysis. The final step was elution, which released the retained compounds from the sorbent into the eluate, yielding purified analytes ready for further analytical procedures (Płotka-Wasyłka et al. 2016).

To achieve optimal extraction efficiency, the SPE system was subjected to systematic optimization, as illustrated in Fig. 5. MISPE required conditioning to ensure reproducible analyte interaction. The conditioning of the MISPE system was performed through the sequential application of MET and ACN as organic solvents, followed by water. This process was carried out in accordance with a modified SPE protocol previously used for the separation of triazole antifungal agents (Bashir et al. 2020). Following the conditioning step, various solvents—ACN, water, MET, DCM, CHL, and their combinations—were tested to identify the most suitable sample-loading solvent. Results indicated that a 1:1 (v/v) mixture of ACN and water yielded the highest retention of triazole template molecules on the MIP sorbent, outperforming the other solvents tested. During sample loading, MIP sorbents can adsorb target molecules either through specific or nonspecific interactions. Therefore, an appropriate washing step is critical to remove nonspecifically bound compounds while preserving specific binding within the sorbent. The selected washing solvent must effectively disrupt nonspecific interactions with triazole molecules without affecting those that are specifically bound (Li et al. 2019).

Table 3. Summary of analytical method validation results for raw materials.

Parameter	Fluconazole	Voriconazole	Itraconazole
Line equation	$y = 85,597x + 7,084.0$	$y = 58,980x + 1,480.7$	$y = 126,056x + 846.63$
Correlation coefficient (R)	0.999	1.000	1.000
Standard deviation of $\times (V_{x_0})$	4.95	1.57	3.92
Limit of detection (LoD)	0.60 mg/L	0.18 mg/L	0.45 mg/L
Limit of quantification (LoQ)	1.82 mg/L	0.55 mg/L	1.37 mg/L
Accuracy and precision (80%)	Rec. 99.9%, RSD 0.8%	Rec. 100.4%, RSD: 0.1%	Rec. 98.4%, RSD: 0.1%
Accuracy and precision (100%)	Rec. 99.5%, RSD: 0.4%	Rec. 99.6%, RSD: 0.3%	Rec. 100.5%, RSD: 0.3%
Accuracy and precision (120%)	Rec. 98.4%, RSD: 0.3%	Rec. 98.3%, RSD: 0.1%	Rec. 100.3%, RSD: 0.2%
Intermediate precision	$P(t \geq 2.57) = 0.112^*$ $P(\text{RSD} \leq 2\%) = 0.993^{**}$	$P(t \geq 2.57) = 0.109^*$ $P(\text{RSD} \leq 2\%) = 1.000^{**}$	$P(t \geq 2.57) = 0.109^*$ $P(\text{RSD} \leq 2\%) = 0.993^{**}$

*The paired t-test shows no significant difference between the mean recovery of the first and second days.

** The chi-square test indicates that the RSD is not significantly less than 2%.

Figure 5. Optimization of sample loading (a), washing (b), eluting (c), and extraction efficiency result (d).

Among the tested solvents, water demonstrated the highest selectivity, as evidenced by the minimal release of template molecules during the washing phase, confirming its suitability for this step.

Following the washing step, the elution process was optimized to effectively disrupt the interactions between the MIP and the template molecules at the binding sites. The choice of elution solvent was guided by the solubility characteristics of the triazole compounds and their hydrogen-bonding interactions with the sorbent. This strategy ensured the selective release of target molecules by weakening the noncovalent associations between the MIP and the template. A range of solvents was evaluated to determine the one providing the highest recovery of the template. After elution, the samples were evaporated to dryness and reconstituted in the mobile phase before being injected into the HPLC system. Among the solvents evaluated, MET was found to be the most effective eluent, providing superior recovery compared with the others. Extraction efficiency was further evaluated by comparing the recovery of triazole standard solutions processed through the optimized MISPE system with that of standard solutions directly injected into the HPLC. The results demonstrated that recovery rates for triazole standards ranged from 90% to 98%, indicating high extraction efficiency. Based on these findings, triazole standards processed via the MISPE method were used as references in subsequent bioanalytical method analyses.

Plasma sample preparation

The performance of the optimized MISPE system was assessed for the analysis of human plasma samples. A spiked-sample approach was used, in which plasma was supplemented with a 2.5 mg/L standard solution of triazole antifungal agents. Before MISPE extraction, a deproteinization step was performed on the plasma, followed by vortex mixing and centrifugation to reduce matrix interferences, particularly those caused by endogenous plasma proteins (Xu et al. 2019). The impact of matrix effects was further evaluated by optimizing the plasma-to-standard volume ratio. A higher ratio of plasma to organic solvent reduced the matrix effect, as illustrated in Fig. 6. A plasma-to-triazole standard ratio of 1:5 was found to be the most effective in minimizing matrix-related interferences during analysis. The supernatant was then passed through the MISPE cartridge. Conditioning, loading, washing, and eluting were carried out before reconstitution and injection into the HPLC system. As illustrated in Fig. 7, the fluconazole peak in the chromatogram overlapped with endogenous plasma components without sample preparation using MISPE, making accurate quantification unfeasible. However, after applying the MISPE procedure, a distinct separation between the fluconazole and plasma peaks was achieved. These findings reveal that the optimized MISPE system efficiently isolates and separates triazole antifungal compounds from complex plasma matrices. This successful separation process highlights the system's ability to selectively target

Figure 6. Matrix interference analysis.

and extract antifungal agents while minimizing interference from surrounding biological components. The performance of the system underscores its potential as a reliable tool for the analysis and selective separation of triazole compounds in biological samples.

Bioanalytical method validation

Bioanalytical method validation is a critical step in developing analytical procedures for drug quantification in biological matrices. This process ensures that the analytical method produces reliable results with acceptable levels of accuracy, precision, and specificity. Method validation must be conducted in accordance with established regulatory guidelines. Two principal references commonly used for bioanalytical method validation are the U.S.

Food and Drug Administration (FDA) “Guidance for Industry” and the International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) M10 “Guideline on Bioanalytical Method Validation”. According to these guidelines, essential validation parameters include selectivity, linearity, accuracy, precision, and stability, all of which are necessary to ensure the method’s suitability for its intended analytical application (Moein et al. 2017). The analytical method developed in this study is a modified version of previously validated protocols. The chromatographic conditions were adapted from the work of Choudhary et al. (2021), while the protein-precipitation step follows the procedure described by Xu et al. (2019). The main modification lies in the implementation of a molecularly imprinted solid-phase extraction (MISPE) technique, developed in our laboratory to enhance plasma-sample cleanup. Because the core elements of the method had already been validated, a full revalidation was not deemed necessary. Instead, partial validation was performed, focusing on critical parameters including the calibration curve, accuracy, and precision (Moein et al. 2017).

A calibration curve is a bioanalytical parameter that describes the relationship between analyte concentration and the corresponding chromatographic response. It is assessed by analyzing blank matrix samples spiked with an internal standard and a series of six calibration levels ranging from the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) to the upper limit of quantification (ULOQ). The resulting calibration curve is used to generate a simple linear-regression equation that reflects the correlation between analyte concentration and instrument response. Calibration curves must be constructed in at least three independent runs on separate days to ensure reproducibility. According to validation

Figure 7. Plasma chromatogram: direct injection (top) and MISPE-prepared sample (bottom).

guidelines, the back-calculated concentrations for each calibration point must fall within $\pm 20\%$ of the nominal value for the LLOQ level to be considered acceptable (Kaza et al. 2019). Linearity assessment was conducted over the concentration range of 0.5–5.0 mg/L, in accordance with the recommended therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) range for triazole antifungal agents (Gómez-López 2020). The relationship between analyte concentration and peak area was evaluated, resulting in a linear-regression equation and correlation-coefficient values as presented in Table 4. The linearity test demonstrated that the mean %bias for all seven concentration levels met the acceptance criteria, with deviations within $\pm 20\%$ for the LLOQ (0.5 mg/L) and within $\pm 15\%$ for the remaining concentrations.

Accuracy is a validation parameter that reflects the closeness of the measured value to the nominal or true value, whereas precision indicates the degree of agreement among replicate measurements under specified conditions. The assessment of accuracy and precision was carried out using quality-control (QC) samples at four distinct concentration levels: LLOQ, low QC, medium QC, and high QC, with a minimum of five replicates at each level. These parameters were assessed through two types of testing—within-run (intra-assay) and between-run (inter-assay) analyses. According to validation guidelines, the accuracy for each concentration level must fall within $\pm 15\%$ of the nominal value, except for the LLOQ level, which is allowed a deviation of up to $\pm 20\%$. Similarly, the precision, expressed as the coefficient of variation (%RSD), should not exceed 15% for all QC levels, with an acceptable limit of up to 20% for the LLOQ (Kadian et al. 2016).

Table 5 presents the results of accuracy and precision testing for voriconazole (VOR), itraconazole (ITR), and fluconazole (FLU) at four QC levels: LLOQ (0.5 mg/L), low QC (1.0 mg/L), medium QC (2.5 mg/L), and high QC (5.0 mg/L). The evaluation was conducted over three separate days, with five replicates per day for within-run analysis ($n = 5$) and a total of fifteen replicates for between-run analysis ($n = 15$). The data demonstrate that all measured values adhered to established validation criteria. Specifically, %bias and %RSD for LLOQ did not exceed 20%, while values for QCL, QCM, and QCH remained within 15%. These findings confirm that the method exhibits acceptable levels of trueness and repeatability under both intra- and inter-day conditions, thereby supporting its reliability for quantitative analysis in a bioanalytical context.

Comparison with the established method

The efficacy of the MISPE sorbent was assessed relative to that of commercially available C_{18} SPE cartridges. Existing studies have employed C_{18} as the predominant sorbent for the separation of triazole antifungals in bioanalysis due to its effectiveness in retaining a broad range of nonpolar and moderately polar substances from aqueous biological matrices, including blood plasma and urine (Sentellas et al. 2020; Tanaka et al. 2022). Experimental results indicated that MISPE exhibited a higher affinity for triazole antifungal agents, as reflected in significantly greater analyte recoveries than those obtained using C_{18} SPE, as shown in Fig. 8. Furthermore, MISPE demonstrated enhanced selectivity relative to C_{18} SPE, indicative of effective

Table 4. Linearity of the bioanalytical method.

Concentration (mg/L)	Bias VOR (%)	Bias ITR (%)	Bias FLU (%)
0.5	12.4	11.1	13.4
1.0	9.4	10.3	11.7
2.0	11.2	12.0	8.9
2.5	11.9	12.6	6.1
3.0	11.3	10.7	10.3
4.0	7.4	9.9	9.3
5.0	9.7	9.4	8.2
Regression equation	$y = 42702x + 1890.9$	$y = 91982x + 3561.5$	$y = 5793.7x + 58175$
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.986	0.990	0.914

Table 5. Accuracy and precision of the bioanalytical method.

Concentration (mg/L)	Day	<i>Within run</i> (n = 5)						<i>Between run</i> (n = 15)					
		Bias (%)			RSD (%)			Bias (%)			RSD (%)		
		VOR	ITR	FLU	VOR	ITR	FLU	VOR	ITR	FLU	VOR	ITR	FLU
0.5	1	12.2	10.7	11.2	8.4	9.7	9.5	13.0	12.5	13.2	7.5	10.9	11.1
	2	12.7	12.5	15.6	7.1	12.1	12.9						
	3	14.2	14.3	12.9	6.9	10.9	10.8						
1.0	1	8.4	7.3	10.6	7.5	7.3	6.9	8.5	9.1	11.0	6.0	6.9	5.8
	2	7.8	11.7	12.9	4.9	6.4	6.1						
	3	9.2	8.3	9.5	5.7	7.1	4.4						
2.5	1	10.9	9.9	8.1	5.0	6.0	4.0	9.8	10.8	8.3	5.5	5.3	6.1
	2	8.4	12.0	5.7	6.5	5.3	7.8						
	3	10.2	10.5	11.1	4.9	4.6	6.5						
5.0	1	8.7	8.7	5.2	4.7	2.9	3.3	9.0	9.3	8.3	4.1	4.3	5.2
	2	8.1	8.2	8.2	4.2	4.7	5.7						
	3	10.2	10.8	11.5	3.5	5.4	6.5						

Figure 8. Comparison of MISPE sorbent with C_{18} SPE.

molecular imprinting. The MIP sorbent was synthesized using triazole antifungal compounds as template molecules, resulting in the formation of specific recognition cavities within the polymer matrix that are complementary in shape, size, and functional group orientation to the target analytes (Sadia et al. 2023). The selective binding interactions between the analytes and the imprinted recognition sites in MISPE were more pronounced than the nonspecific interactions typically observed with conventional C_{18} SPE (Suryana et al. 2022). These findings confirm the superior recognition capabilities of MISPE for the targeted extraction of triazole antifungals from complex biological matrices.

Conclusion

This study successfully developed and validated a high-performance liquid chromatography method with ultraviolet detection (HPLC–UV), integrated with an MISPE protocol, for the simultaneous quantification of VOR, ITR, and FLU in human plasma. The optimal system was achieved using a C_{18} column with a water–acetonitrile (30:70, v/v) mobile phase under isocratic elution, a 1.0 mL/min flow rate, a 50 μ L injection volume, and detection at 260 nm, with a total retention time of 10 minutes. A spiked-sample approach was employed for method validation. Before extraction, plasma samples underwent protein precipitation followed by vortex mixing and centrifugation, after which the supernatant was cleaned using the MISPE sorbent. Optimization of the conditioning, loading, washing, and eluting steps of the MISPE method provided outstanding recovery rates ranging from 90% to 98%, indicating high extraction efficiency. Raw-materials method validation was performed in accordance with established regulatory guidelines, showing a correlation coefficient of linearity ≥ 0.999 over a 0.5–5 mg/L range. Accuracy showed recoveries between 98.3% and 100.5%, with %RSD values of precision $\leq 0.8\%$, demonstrating the method's capability to detect and quantify low analyte concentrations with sufficient sensitivity for subsequent bioanalytical applications.

Bioanalytical method validation demonstrated linearity over the 0.5–5 mg/L range, with maximum percent bias values of 13.4% for the calibration curve, 15.6% at the LLOQ, and 12.9% above the LLOQ. Precision showed a maximum coefficient of variation of 12.9%, confirming the method's accuracy and reproducibility. These results confirm the reliability, accuracy, and reproducibility of the method for quantitative bioanalysis applications. MISPE demonstrated markedly enhanced selectivity compared with conventional C_{18} SPE cartridges. The improved analytical performance observed with MISPE highlights its potential as a robust and reliable sample-preparation technique for trace-level analysis of structurally defined compounds in clinical applications. Further studies involving real clinical specimens are warranted to establish the method's applicability for routine therapeutic drug monitoring and pharmacokinetic investigations.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

Dion Notario: Validation, Writing – review & editing. Untung Gunawan: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft. Eko Adi Prasetyanto: Project administration, Writing – review & editing. Patrick Renata: Data curation, Investigation. Atthar Luqman Ivansyah: Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Statistical data of intermediate precision

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Data type: xlsx

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